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The current impediments and prospects of 'Container Train Operators' in India.

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Abstract

Indian railways are under the control of the government which is the sole provider of the infrastructure, operations and regulatory functions.

In January 2006, in a landmark initiative to introduce competition in the container operations segment, the Ministry of Railways allowed the entry of private and public sector operators to obtain licences for running container trains on the Indian Railways (IR) network. Until then, the Container Corporation of India, a subsidiary of IR, was the monopoly operator of container trains in India. This initiative was the first significant move of its kind where private parties were allowed to make entry in the domain of railway operations with direct customer interfacing.

About 16 container train operators (CTOs) which have been inducted by Indian Railways (IR) in intermodal business in January 2006, then touted as the first revolutionary public-private partnership (PPP) initiative in rail operations taken by IR, "are feeling without steam". What began as a euphoric response from several renowned Indian and overseas firms in the shipping & logistics sector seems to be sputtering out.

CTOs are concerned at the lack of clarity on some of the basic issues, for example, the use of railway terminals and private rail sidings for carrying domestic traffic. Other concerning issues are service guarantees, rating & pricing policy, maintenance of rolling stocks, commodities which railways do not permit in containers, and most of all, difficulties in acquiring land for intermodal terminals.

This paper examines the current policy environment from the point of view of business viability for 16 new Container Train Operators and brings out issues related to licensing, pricing, terminals, maintenance, and service levels.

Keywords: *Container Train Operators, Container Corporation of India, Indian Railways, Policy Issues for Container Transport*

Introduction

Statement of the Problem